

WEAR CHARACTERISTICS OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Effects of fiber orientation on friction and wear of graphite fiber composites were investigated experimentally. Graphite fiber composites were produced by the vacuum bag molding using an autoclave and machined to specimens of specific fiber orientations. Pin on disk type testing machine was built to measure the friction coefficient and wear rate with different fiber orientations, i.e., normal, transverse, and longitudinal directions. Three different wear conditions were employed for the test. The worn surface of the specimen was examined with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to observe the damaged fibers on the surface. The damage mechanism of the fibers during sliding wear was speculated based on the experimental data and the microscopic observations.

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites are nowadays used extensively for tribological applications. Various fillers and reinforcements have been added to polymeric substances to improve strength and wear characteristics. For example, a wide variety of polymeric composites are available today for use as bearing materials, including self-lubricating reinforced plastics which contain solid lubricant such as Teflon, MoS₂, or graphite powders. Experimental and theoretical studies on wear behavior of fiber composites under various conditions have been reported, e.g., sliding wear, abrasive wear, erosive wear, and fretting. Tsukizoe and Ohmae [1-3] and Sung and Suh [4] studied the effect of fiber orientation on sliding wear of graphite fiber composites. Tsukizoe and Ohmae reported that the high modulus carbon fiber composite has the lowest wear in the transverse sliding direction and the high strength carbon fiber composite in the longitudinal direction. The maximum wear occurs in the longitudinal direction for the high modulus fiber composite and in the transverse direction for the high strength fiber composite. They also claimed that both high modulus and high strength carbon fiber composites experienced seizure in the normal sliding direction. According to Sung and Suh, the minimum wear of the carbon fiber composite was obtained in the normal sliding direction and the maximum wear in the transverse direction. Any seizure has not been reported in the normal direction.

Wear mechanisms of composites in different sliding directions or fiber orientations must be understood well in order to design a good wear resistant composite structure for specific sliding applications. The high modulus carbon fiber composites showed good wear resistance because the graphitized high modulus carbon fiber composite generates surface wear film which reduces friction and wear owing to the self-lubricating nature of graphite powders. Effects of fiber orientation on sliding wear of unidirectional carbon fiber composites vary depending upon the reinforcing fiber and the sliding condition. The high modulus carbon fiber composite was selected for investigation of wear behavior in different sliding conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

A unidirectional carbon fiber composite plate was produced by laminating the prepreg and curing in an autoclave with a vacuum bag. Specimens of size 4.5mm X 5.5mm X 10mm were prepared with three fiber orientations, normal, longitudinal, and transverse. The sliding surface of the specimen was carefully prepared by grinding and polishing followed by cleaning with a mild detergent, water, and hexane. A pin-on-disk type experimental setup shown in Fig.1 was built. The frictional force was measured by a load cell and recorded continuously in a personal computer (IBM PC/AT) using an A/D converter and an amplifier. A counterface, a stainless steel (SUS 304) disk, was prepared by grinding and polishing with a fine abrasive paper to give surface roughness of 0.02 μ m. Three wear test conditions were employed; in condition I sliding speed of 0.5 m/s and normal load of 19.6 N was employed, in condition II 0.5 m/s and 49 N was employed, and in condition III 2.5 m/s and 19.6 N was employed. The friction and wear test was conducted for 24 hours for each specimen in each condition. The frictional force was measured continuously and the weight loss was measured after the test had been completed. Friction coefficients and wear factors were calculated based on the measurements. Wear track of the worn specimen was carefully examined with a SEM to observe the wear film formation and damaged fibers which were exposed at the surface.

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the pin-on-disk set-up

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When the specimens were tested under the condition I, the weight loss was too small to measure after 24 hour sliding. It means that the applied stresses on the surface was not large enough to cause considerable fiber failure in this light wear condition. The friction coefficient was the highest in the normal direction (0.27), the lowest in the longitudinal direction (0.18), and middle in the transverse direction (0.23). When tested under the condition II, the friction coefficient in the longitudinal direction increased to 0.65, that in the normal direction decreased to 0.2, and that in the transverse direction decreased to 0.15 as shown in Fig. 2. The condition II caused maximum wear in the longitudinal direction and minimum wear in the normal direction (Fig. 3). Micrographs of the worn surface of the specimens are shown in Fig. 4. The polished cross-section of the fibers were observed on the worn surface in the normal direction. In the transverse direction, wear film and fibers broken by the counterface asperity motion were found on the wear track as shown in the picture. In the case of the longitudinal sliding, carbon fibers are polished to show flat side surface and some fibers are missing owing to counterface interaction. When the sliding speed was increased from condition I to condition III, the friction

coefficient in each direction did not vary significantly. As illustrated in Fig. 5 the highest friction occurred in the longitudinal direction and the lowest occurred in the transverse direction. Differently from the condition II, the transverse sliding yielded the lowest wear but the highest wear occurred in the same direction as in the condition II (Fig. 6). The microscopic observation of the worn surface in the transverse direction revealed that the wear film covered the surface as shown in Fig. 7. In the case of longitudinally slid specimens the traces of missing fibers were observed. The wear track of the normally oriented specimen showed distinct behavior; the polished cross-section of the normally oriented fibers (Fig. 7) and greatly damaged regions (Fig. 8) were observed. The damaged region, named massive failure region, was created at the moment the frictional force was increased and decreased suddenly with a large noise. When the counter-face was examined, a deep groove was found in the wear track of the disk at the exactly same position where the massive failure region was located. This phenomenon needs more investigation because Tsukizoe and Ohmae reported seizure in the normal direction.

Frictional properties of materials were well explained by Suh and Sin [5]. They proposed that the friction coefficient is composed of three components; one due to the deforming asperities, another due to plowing by wear particles entrapped between the sliding surfaces and hard asperities, and the other due to adhesion. The contribution by the plowing can be greater than that by other components. In the case of condition I, since the wear was negligibly small the contribution of the wear particles to the friction coefficient should be small. In the longitudinal sliding, the counterfaces slide continuously on the carbon fiber which has low friction. Without entrapped fiber debris between the surfaces the friction coefficient in the longitudinal direction will be the lowest. As the sliding speed and the normal load increase the fiber debris are generated and entrapped at the interface to increase the friction coefficient. When the normal load is 19.6 N and the sliding speed is 2.5 m/s the wear film seems to make an important role especially in the transverse direction because the wear film fills the groove between fibers and acts like a solid lubricant. The wear film adhered to the worn surface was also observed in the normally slid specimen. It may be the reason why the friction coefficients in the normal and transverse directions are almost the same in condition III.

Condition I is not severe enough to generate measurable wear in any sliding direction within 24 hours. It is believed that the applied normal and frictional stresses are carried by the fibers without considerable fiber breakage in this condition. With the normal load of 49 N, fibers in the transverse and longitudinal directions must be damaged by bending, buckling, or pulling as the micrographs of the worn surface suggest. In the case of condition II, the normally oriented fibers can support the applied stresses with the least fiber failure. Condition III is the severest wear condition when the PV value is considered. The largest wear was obtained in the longitudinal direction and the SEM picture implied that the fibers were thinned down by grinding and broken away by the asperity motion. In the transverse direction, the fibers are damaged by bending but the fiber breakage is not so severe because of the lubrication effect of wear film. In order to understand the fiber damage mechanism in depth, stress analyses of the subsurface under the applied stresses are needed for each condition and sliding direction. The phenomenon of massive failure region in normal sliding direction requires more experiments and theoretical analyses for better explanation.

CONCLUSIONS

Friction and wear behavior of unidirectional carbon fiber composite material varies according to sliding conditions and fiber orientation against the sliding direction. In light sliding conditions, the friction coefficient is the highest in normal direction and the lowest in longitudinal direction while the wear is negligibly small in any sliding direction. As the conditions become severe, the friction coefficient in longitudinal direction is the highest and that in transverse direction is the lowest. The magnitude of the friction coefficient depends strongly on the

fiber debris generation and the wear film interaction. The highest wear is also obtained in the longitudinal direction and the lowest wear in the normal direction for condition II and in the transverse direction for condition III. The fiber damage mechanism will be bending, buckling, or pulling depending upon the situation.

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Fig. 2 Coefficients of friction of the composites in the different sliding directions (Sliding speed = 0.5 m/s, Normal load = 5 kgf)

Fig. 3 Wear factors of the composites in the different sliding directions. (Sliding speed = 0.5 m/s, Normal load = 5 kgf)

Fig. 5 Coefficients of friction of the composites in the different sliding directions (Sliding speed = 2.5 m/s, Normal load = 2 kgf)

Fig. 6 Wear factors of the composites in the different sliding directions. (Sliding speed = 2.5 m/s, Normal load = 2 kgf)

a) Longitudinal

b) Transverse

c) Normal

Fig. 7 Micrographs of the wear track for different fiber orientation (sliding speed=2.5 m/s, normal load=19.6N)

Fig. 8 Micrograph of the massive failure region in the wear track of the worn specimen with normal fiber orientation.

a) Longitudinal

b) Transverse

c) Normal

Fig. 4 Micrographs of the wear track for different fiber orientation (sliding speed=0.5 m/s, normal load=49N)